

Aging Research Idea Generator: a web application to AI-based generation of new ideas for aging research

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Abstract

As aging is one of the main challenges of our society, we need increasingly more research ideas to solve the problems of aging biology. To accelerate aging research, here, we tailored the scientific idea generation part of the AI Scientist workflow to aging research and developed an easy-to-use web server implementation of it, called the Aging Research Idea Generator (ARIG). Using the title and abstract of a published research paper or a preprint as an input, ARIG generates a new idea and a corresponding mini-proposal that can serve as a continuation (i.e., the next step) of the input study. We evaluated the application by using 10 of our previous studies (from the field of aging biology, aging clocks, and bioinformatics) as input and found all of the generated ideas highly relevant and useful. Impressed by the capabilities of ARIG, we decided to share it with the community. While each idea generation query has a cost, we made it freely available for researchers in the hope that the tool will

accelerate aging research by providing useful ideas to a large number of researchers in the field. The ARIG tool is available at <https://ideagenerator.sztaki.hu>.

Introduction

Population aging, with the rising incidence of aging-related diseases, is a big challenge of the 21st century; hence, there is an increasing need for aging research. The field of aging science has gone through remarkable progress in recent decades; however, the underlying mechanisms of aging and many other fundamental questions remain unanswered^{1,2}. Science, including aging biology research, is driven by new research ideas. Research ideas often come when a scientist is thinking about the next step of a research paper. Here, we aimed to automate this process by comparing an input research paper to the whole relevant scientific literature to generate new research ideas for aging research.

Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) and foundation models have significantly improved the ability of artificial intelligence to process and interpret unstructured scientific text (Anthropic Sonnet³, Google Gemini⁴, Llama⁵, and OpenAI GPT^{6,7}). These models are capable of summarizing scientific articles and answering domain-specific questions. When combined with external tools such as literature search, code execution, and persistent memory, LLMs can be extended into AI agents capable of performing more complex reasoning and multi-step workflows. This development has led to interest in AI-assisted scientific discovery systems. Such systems aim to assist—or potentially automate—various stages of the scientific process, including idea generation. Demonstrating the potential of these approaches, Sakana AI introduced an end-to-end autonomous research agent capable of generating machine learning research papers, starting with the idea generation phase⁸⁻¹⁰. Other studies have explored the use of LLM-based systems for

specifically scientific idea generation and validation¹¹⁻¹³. However, these systems often are not easy to use for a typical researcher and are not specifically designed for the generation of ideas and mini-proposals for aging research. To fill this gap, here, we tailored the scientific idea generation part of the existing AI Scientist v2 workflow⁹ for aging research, and implemented it as an easy-to-use web application. In our implementation, the system starts from an existing scientific article (for example, the user's recently published paper) and proposes potential new research directions that extend the original work.

Results

We implemented the scientific idea generation part of the AI Scientist workflow into an easy-to-use web application and tailored it for an aging research idea generator. The tool is available for researchers upon registration without cost. It allows users to search in PubMed for finding an input paper; however, users can also copy-paste a custom abstract of a preprint or unpublished research. Once the input is submitted, a background process on the server initiates the idea generation workflow (Fig. 1). After completion, the generated research idea is displayed in the form of a structured miniproposal including (i) a short hypothesis, (ii) related work with literature references, (iii) proposed abstract, (iv) suggested experiments, and (v) potential risks and limitations (Fig. 2). The tool generates only one idea at once for simplicity. The user has the option to re-generate an idea for the same abstract. Additionally, features include that users can export generated ideas as text files, revisit previously generated ideas from their history, and provide like or dislike feedback for each generated idea. This feedback is stored in the system database to support later-stage evaluation of the generated ideas and to provide input for future fine-tuning. The web server is publicly available at <https://ideagenerator.sztaki.hu>

Discussion

The Aging Research Idea Generator (ARIG) is an easy-to-use web tool for generating new research ideas from an input paper. As good research ideas often come after reading a research paper, we designed the tool to point out a possible next step or a new direction of the research. We evaluated the application by using 10 of our previous studies (from the field of aging biology, aging clocks, and bioinformatics) as input and found all of the generated ideas highly relevant and useful (see the discussion of all in the Supplementary Information). Because the input studies came from our own research domain, we could evaluate the generated directions within a familiar scientific context and assess their relevance with confidence. For example, using a study on increased biological age by stress and restoration upon recovery¹⁴ as an input, the ARIG pointed out that the critical questions of who recovers, how quickly, and what predicts successful recovery remain unanswered. The generated proposal (also can be seen in Fig. 2) suggested tracking biological age recovery at 2 weeks, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months post-surgery, measuring not only epigenetic, RNA-seq, metabolomics, cortisol patterns, heart rate variability, inflammatory markers, and mitochondrial function assays. Most importantly, ARIG creatively suggested using machine learning to identify baseline molecular and physiological signatures that predict recovery speed (time to return to baseline biological age) and completeness (final biological age relative to baseline). To our knowledge, this idea is highly novel. Impressed by the capabilities of ARIG, we decided to share it with the community. We intended to use it for aging research, and tested mostly for aging research papers. However, because it uses PubMed, Google Search Semantic Scholar for novelty checking, it may also work for the broader life sciences. The tool can not guarantee that the generated idea is novel or even feasible, but an experienced researcher (the user) can decide.

Methods

Workflow the Aging Research Idea Generator

Here, we provided the workflow of ARIG, which is the adaptation of the workflow of the AI Scientist v2⁹ (please, see our changes compared to the original prompts in the Supplementary Information).

The tool first builds the starting context. The essence of seed logic is that you need a core: an existing scientific article to which the new idea will be "related but new." Here, the seed can be: (i) existing article metadata (title, authors, year, venue, etc.), or (ii) a title and abstract. This seed is entered into the `workshop_description` field (in the prompt's terminology, "workshop description") and becomes the basis for idea generation. The purpose of the seed phase is therefore not generation, but context loading and grounding: the subsequent idea must feed on this.

Once the seed context is available, the first "substantive" generation step begins, in which the model's task is to create an interesting, novel, grant-proposal-style research idea that explicitly indicates how it differs from the existing literature and is feasible at the laboratory level. Here, the system uses a highly detailed system prompt (see "system_prompt" in Supplementary Information) to set the style, framework, output format, and available tools. The system is implemented using the Anthropic API with the Claude-4-Sonnet (20250514) model. It is important to note that at this stage, the system already requires at least one literature search before finalization. In this phase, the tool creates a first version that is not yet final: its purpose is to lay down the direction and framework of the hypothesis so that it can then be improved through research and reflection.

In the next step, the tool searches for literature based on the first idea. Here, the operating concept is that the system runs a full-text search using a query generated from the idea. The tool retrieves a maximum of 10 PubMed results, 10 Google Search results and 10 Semantic Scholar results (including bioarxiv and medarxiv), ranked by relevance. The search results are fed back into the next reflection cycle, so the search output is not an "end product" but input for refinement.

The tool then enters an iterative reflection cycle, where in each round, the model evaluates the quality of the current idea based on its novelty and feasibility, and improves the idea in light of the results obtained by the tool. The reflection prompt (see "idea_reflection_prompt" in Supplementary Information) explicitly asks the model not to overcomplicate things, to keep the spirit, and to deviate significantly only if there are "glaring issues". In addition, the Round $\{\text{current_round}\}/\{\text{num_reflections}\}$ mechanic is hard-coded into the prompt, making it clear that this is a process with a maximum of N rounds. It is crucial here that search results are specifically injected into the prompt: thus, search results are not incidental, but rather the primary basis for refinement. This ensures that the idea is not only creative but also well-founded in relation to the literature.

Then the tool repeats: (i) current version of the idea, (ii) search (max. 10), (iii) reflection, (iv) improved idea, until it reaches the max iteration (max. 5), or the model decides that the idea is good enough and takes action `FinalizeIdea`. According to the operational description, the tool refines each idea in a maximum of 5 steps and returns one idea for each request. This means that there is no "idea list" output; the pipeline refines a single idea iteratively. The process is considered successful if the model selects the `FinalizeIdea` action and returns the idea in the specified JSON structure. The fields specified in the `FinalizeIdea` definition are not merely for documentation purposes, but force the model output into a format suitable for downstream processing.

Data and code availability

We adapted the codes of the AI Scientist v2 tool available here: https://github.com/SakanaAI/AI-Scientist-v2/blob/main/ai_scientist/perform_ideation_temp_free.py. We highlighted the changes in the prompts that we made in the Supplementary Information. The ARIG is available at <https://ideagenerator.sztaki.hu>.

Author contributions

C.K. conceived and supervised the study. K.S. developed the Aging Research Idea Generator. All authors edited the manuscript.

Acknowledgments

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Declaration of interest

None.

FIGURES

Fig. 1. | Workflow of the Aging Research Idea Generator (ARIG). The user selects an input article, and the tool reads its title and abstract. In *Step 1*, the system generates an idea that is related to the input study but aims to be new. In this phase, the tool creates a first

version of the idea, laying down the direction and the framework of the hypothesis. In *Step 2*, once the candidate idea is available, the system checks its novelty by fetching related articles from PubMed, Google Search and Semantic Scholar (including bioarxiv and medarxiv). The tool searches the literature using the first idea and retrieves a maximum of 10 PubMed results, 10 Google Search results and 10 Semantic Scholar results, ranked by relevance. In *Step 3*, the system evaluates whether the generated idea shows substantial similarity to the most relevant existing works found in the literature search. If the idea appears to be too similar to previous work, the system enters the next refinement iteration. In *Step 4*, the system enters an iterative reflection cycle. In each round, the model evaluates the current idea based on its quality, novelty, and feasibility, and then improves the idea in light of the literature search results obtained by the tool. The cycles continue until the system reaches five iterations, unless the idea is good enough to finalize it (*Step 5*).

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Generate New Ideas

Search...

EXAMPLES

Insulin & Senescence
Multifactorial single-cell perturbation s...
Deciphering Metabolic Senescence Subtypes through...

Macrophage Senescence
SIRT1/6-mediated senescent macrophag...
Deciphering How Senescent Macrophages Evade Immune...

DC Aging & Vaccines
Alleviating age-related decline in d...
Age-related mitochondrial dysfunction impairs the...

Metabolism & Immunity
The glycolytic metabolic phenotype...
Systematic Discovery of Glycolytic and TCA Cycle...

Neuroend Aging
Aging effects delineate neuron type...
Metabolic State-Dependent Neuronal Aging Trajectories...

Microglia Aging
Simultaneous spatial transcriptomic...
Deciphering the Molecular Machinery of mRNA Trafficking...

APOE4 & Alzheimer's
Neuronal APOE4-induced early hippoc...
Neuronal APOE4-induced hyperexcitability primes...

Vascular Dementia
Reprogramming drugs for the preventi...
Temporal Dynamics of Beta-1 Selective Antagonism in...

Breast Tissue Aging
Single-cell spatial atlas of the aging...
Mechanical Force Transmission Networks Drive Age-Related...

Sex & Immunosenescence
Single-cell analysis of the human X...
X-chromosome inactivation Dynamics Drive Sex-Specific...

HISTORY

Face photo-based age acceleration predicts all-cau...
gen_2025-05-04T11:28-05_05094

Biological age is increased by stress and restored upon...
gen_2025-05-02T18:56-05_02024

How to Direct the Edges of the Connectomes: Dynamics of...
gen_2025-05-02T18:57-05_02041

Epigenetic clocks reveal a rejuvenation event during...
gen_2025-05-02T18:57-05_02097

Intersection clock reveals a rejuvenation event during...
gen_2025-05-02T18:57-05_02098

Human Brain Cell-Type-Specific Aging Clocks Based...
gen_2025-05-02T08:44-05_02049

Profiling the transcriptomic age of single-cells in humans...
gen_2025-05-02T08:35-05_02042

Physical Fitness is Negatively Associated With DNA...
gen_2025-04-29T11:03-04_34f86

N/A
gen_2025-04-28T10:51-02_01040

Profiling the transcriptomic age of single-cells in humans...
gen_2025-04-28T05:18-05_01034

Seed Article

Biological age is increased by stress and restored upon recovery.

Jeske R Poganki, Bohan Zhang, Gurpreet S Bhatt, Alexander Tyshkovskiy, Amy J Dahl, Csaba Kerepesi, Sun-Hye Yim, Alex T Lu, Armin Haghighi, Tong Gong, Anna M Hedman, Erika Andolf, Göran Pershagen, Catalina Almqvist, Clary B Clish, Steve Horvath, James P White, Vadim M Gladyshev

[Cell metabolism](#) 2023 PMID: 37085720

Aging is classically conceptualized as an ever-increasing trajectory of damage accumulation and loss of function, leading to increases in morbidity and mortality. However, recent in vitro studies have raised the possibility of age reversal. Here, we report that biological age is fluid and exhibits rapid changes in both directions. At epigenetic, transcriptomic, and metabolomic levels, we find that the biological age of young mice is increased by heterochronic parabiosis and restored following surgical detachment. We also identify transient changes in biological age during major surgery, pregnancy, and severe COVID-19 in humans and/or mice. Together, these data show that biological age undergoes a rapid increase in response to diverse forms of stress, which is reversed following recovery from stress. Our study uncovers a new layer of aging dynamics that should be considered in future studies. The elevation of biological age by stress may be a quantifiable and actionable target for future interventions.

Generated Research Idea

Like
Dislike
Copy
Export
Regenerate
Delete

Predicting Biological Age Recovery: Identifying Molecular and Physiological Markers of Stress-Induced Aging Reversibility

Generation ID: gen_2025-05-02T18-06-25_0202f

Short Hypotheses

Individual differences in biological age recovery following stress can be predicted by baseline molecular signatures and physiological resilience markers, enabling personalized interventions for accelerated aging reversal. While Poganki et al. demonstrated that biological age increases with stress and can recover afterward, the critical questions of who recovers, how quickly, and what predicts successful recovery remain unanswered. This represents a fundamental gap in our understanding of aging plasticity that, if addressed, could transform how we approach age-related interventions by identifying individuals most likely to benefit from specific recovery protocols.

Related Work

Poganki et al. (*Cell Metabolism*, 2023) established that biological age increases with stress and recovers upon stress removal in mice and humans, but did not investigate individual differences in recovery dynamics or predictive markers. Pyrkov et al. (*medRxiv*, 2020) identified resilience markers from wearable sensors but focused on general health outcomes rather than biological age recovery specifically. Olde Rikkert et al. (*Frontiers in Physiology*, 2019) proposed dynamic resilience biomarkers for recovery prediction in geriatric medicine, but did not apply these concepts to epigenetic age or stress-induced aging. Recent epigenetic clock studies (Eder et al., 2025; Rodrigues et al., 2025) examine stress-aging relationships but treat biological age as a static outcome rather than investigating recovery dynamics. Our proposal uniquely focuses on the understudied recovery phase, combining baseline predictive markers with longitudinal recovery tracking to identify molecular determinants of aging reversibility.

Proposed Abstract

Biological age can increase rapidly under stress and recover afterward, but individual recovery varies dramatically. We propose to identify predictive markers of biological age recovery by conducting a longitudinal study of 200 healthy adults (25-65 years) undergoing planned surgical stress. Participants will be assessed at baseline, immediately post-surgery (stress peak), and during 6-month recovery using multiple epigenetic clocks (GrimAge2, DunedinPACE), transcriptomics, metabolomics, and physiological resilience markers. We hypothesize that baseline molecular signatures—including inflammatory gene expression patterns, mitochondrial function markers, and stress response pathway activity—will predict recovery speed and completeness. We will develop a machine learning model integrating baseline omics data, physiological measurements (heart rate variability, cortisol patterns), and demographic factors to predict individual recovery trajectories. This 'Recovery Predictor Score' will be validated in an independent cohort experiencing different stressors (intensive care patients). The study will establish the first systematic framework for predicting biological age recovery, potentially identifying individuals who would benefit most from specific interventions during the critical recovery window. This work could transform personalized anti-aging medicine by enabling targeted interventions for those at highest risk of persistent biological age acceleration.

Proposed Experiments

- **Baseline Characterization:** Collect comprehensive baseline data from 200 surgical patients including epigenetic clocks (GrimAge2, DunedinPACE), RNA-seq, metabolomics, cortisol patterns, heart rate variability, inflammatory markers (IL-6, TNF- α , CRP), and mitochondrial function assays (Complex I activity, mtDNA copy number)
- **Stress Response Tracking:** Measure biological age acceleration 48-72 hours post-surgery when stress-induced aging peaks, alongside acute stress markers and physiological parameters
- **Recovery Monitoring:** Track biological age recovery at 2 weeks, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months post-surgery, measuring both epigenetic age normalization and molecular pathway restoration
- **Predictive Model Development:** Use machine learning (random forest, gradient boosting) to identify baseline molecular and physiological signatures that predict recovery speed (time to return to baseline biological age) and completeness (final biological age relative to baseline)
- **Validation Cohort:** Test the Recovery Predictor Score in 100 ICU patients experiencing different stressors, measuring prediction accuracy using correlation coefficients between predicted and observed recovery trajectories
- **Mechanistic Analysis:** Perform pathway enrichment analysis on predictive molecular signatures to identify key biological processes underlying recovery capacity, focusing on DNA repair, inflammatory resolution, and cellular stress response pathways

Risks & Limitations

- **Individual Variability:** High inter-individual differences in stress response and recovery may reduce predictive model accuracy, potentially requiring larger sample sizes or population stratification
- **Confounding Factors:** Surgical type, medications, and recovery conditions may introduce variability that complicates interpretation of recovery dynamics
- **Technical Limitations:** Current epigenetic clocks may lack sufficient sensitivity to detect rapid recovery changes, potentially requiring development of more dynamic aging biomarkers
- **Generalizability:** Recovery predictors identified in surgical stress may not apply to other stressors (psychological, environmental, disease-related), limiting broader applicability
- **Time-Intensive Study:** 6-month longitudinal follow-up may result in participant dropout, potentially biasing results toward more compliant or healthier individuals
- **Cost Considerations:** Multi-omics profiling at multiple timepoints requires substantial resources, potentially limiting sample size and statistical power for subgroup analyses

Fig. 2. | An example input and output of the Aging Research Idea Generator. The left panel provides access to previously generated ideas (examples and history). The middle panel shows the input (i.e., the title and abstract of the seed scientific article¹⁴). The right panel displays the output (i.e., the generated research idea/miniproposal): (i) short hypotheses, (ii) related work with literature references, (iii) proposed abstract, (iv) proposed experiments, and (v) potential risks and limitations.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

I. Discussion of the generated ideas

Here, we discuss 10 generated ideas (without selection). The complete proposals (i.e., the extracted outputs of ARIG) are available in the Supplementary Files. In each case, we used our previous study as an input, as we could confidently evaluate the idea in our research topics.

IDEA1. Using the abstract of our recent paper on single-cell transcriptomics aging clocks developed for human blood¹⁵, the ARIG proposed the development of human spatial

transcriptomic aging clocks for different tissues. So, the idea is basically the adaptation of the single-cell aging clocks to spatial transcriptomics, where not only single-cell gene expression data, but also the coordinates of the cells in the tissue-microenvironment are available. Of course, this is a great idea, and we totally agree with ARIG that the proposed work would establish a new paradigm for understanding aging as a spatially-organized process and provide tools for mapping aging landscapes in health and disease. However, we have to note that the current version of ARIG missed a closely related paper that very recently reported a spatial transcriptomics clock for the mouse brain¹⁶. This case emphasizes the importance of manual novelty checks after the idea generation.

IDEA2. In the input study¹⁷, we demonstrated that combining front and side-view photos improves cross-sectional age prediction accuracy. As it was a preprint, we were not able to use PubmedID, but copied and pasted the abstract of the preprint. Using this input, the ARIG correctly pointed out that none of the previous studies specifically examined the temporal consistency of facial age estimates using multiple-angle photos, nor investigated whether multi-view approaches provide more stable longitudinal measurements. The tool proposed to address a critical gap in facial aging research by focusing on measurement stability over time rather than just cross-sectional accuracy, potentially providing more robust tools for longitudinal aging studies, clinical trials of anti-aging interventions, and personalized medicine applications. We performed an additional manual novelty check and found that the generated idea is highly novel.

IDEA3. Using the abstract of our recent study based on the association of fitness measurements and episcore-based disease risk¹⁸, the ARIG proposed the investigation of the short-term causal effect of exercise on episcore-based disease risk. It proposed using three

different exercise intensities (moderate, vigorous, and high-intensity interval training) that make sense. Generally, it can always be a good idea to test cross-sectional results using a clinical trial setting. We performed an additional manual novelty check and found that the generated idea is highly novel. Actually, in the time of this manuscript we have an ongoing yet unpublished (no preprint) study that is similar to this generated idea.

IDEA4. We re-generated an idea from the paper that we used for IDEA1. The ARIG pointed out that „no study has systematically compared single-cell aging clocks across multiple human tissues from the same individuals to understand cross-tissue aging synchrony”. So the tool proposed measurements of different tissues (matched blood, skin from dermal punch biopsy, and subcutaneous adipose tissue). The re-generated idea is similar to the original idea, as both proposed multi-tissue single-cell measurements for humans, but not the same. We performed an additional manual novelty check and found that the generated idea is highly novel.

IDEA5. Using our recent paper on single-cell transcriptomics aging clocks for the human brain¹⁹, ARIG pointed out that no studies have systematically compared aging signatures across mammalian species at single-cell resolution to identify evolutionarily conserved species-specific mechanisms. The idea proposed the development of single-cell brain aging clocks for mouse, rat, rhesus macaque (and naked mole-rats), and leveraging existing human data to compare the single-cell aging of the brain in different species with different maximum lifespan. We note that a related paper was published after the idea generation²⁰.

IDEA6. Previously, we revealed a rejuvenation during human embryogenesis using samples with day scales²¹. Using this study as an input, the ARIG proposed to investigate embryonic

rejuvenation in hour-scale resolution using gastruloid models by collecting samples every 4-6 hours during the critical 48-hour gastrulation window. In the original paper, we analysed only methylation-based age dynamics. The generated proposal suggests a simultaneous DNA methylation, hydroxymethylation, and chromatin accessibility, and time-resolved RNA-seq. It also proposes small molecule inhibitors (5-azacytidine for DNMT inhibition, vitamin C for TET activation) applied at specific timepoints to validate the predicted rejuvenation mechanisms and test causality. In our opinion, it is a very good idea to test the embryonic rejuvenation using gastruloid models. Additionally, it is exciting to do multiple measurements and have an hour-scale resolution.

IDEA7. We also generated a mini-proposal from our early embryonic rejuvenation paper from 2021²². The idea generator suggested selectively activating the molecular pathways responsible for the 'ground zero' age reset in adult cells that would enable targeted age reversal while maintaining cell identity. ARIG proposed single-cell RNA-seq and ATAC-seq measurements on mouse embryos from E3.5 (blastocyst) to E7.5 (post-implantation), and using a computational approach to select a minimal gene set that transiently expresses candidate rejuvenation factors in adult mouse fibroblasts. In our opinion, it is a very good idea to mimic the embryonic rejuvenation (at least partially), similarly to transient reprogramming.

IDEA8. We generated an idea from our early findings when we revealed the consensus connectome dynamic (CCD) of the human brain²³. The ARIG proposed a quite straightforward idea: to test whether the temporal order of edge appearance in CCD recapitulates the actual developmental timeline of connections observed in longitudinal brain imaging data. According to the generated proposal, this validation would be crucial because if CCD truly reflects development, it could provide a powerful tool for understanding brain

maturation from cross-sectional data alone. The ARIG correctly emphasized that a limitation can be that available longitudinal data may not cover the full developmental spectrum implied by CCD, particularly early childhood connections. To our knowledge, this idea is novel.

IDEA9. The next idea was generated using the abstract and title of the study, where we showed that biological age is increased by stress and restored upon recovery¹⁴. The ARIG proposed that while Poganik et al. demonstrated that biological age increases with stress and can recover afterward, the critical questions of who recovers, how quickly, and what predicts successful recovery remain unanswered. The generated proposal suggests tracking biological age recovery at 2 weeks, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months post-surgery, measuring epigenetics, RNA-seq, metabolomics, cortisol patterns, heart rate variability, inflammatory markers, and mitochondrial function assays. Most importantly, it creatively suggests using machine learning to identify baseline molecular and physiological signatures that predict recovery speed (time to return to baseline biological age) and completeness (final biological age relative to baseline). To our knowledge, these ideas are highly novel.

IDEA10. Building on our recent findings that facial aging patterns differ among occupations²⁴, the ARIG hypothesized that different environmental exposures (air pollution, chemical exposure, UV damage, occupational hazards) leave distinct, detectable signatures in facial aging patterns. The idea proposes developing a multi-task deep learning framework trained on large-scale facial image datasets with associated environmental and occupational metadata. We note that some aspects, such as sun exposure, have already been analysed by human guess-based age prediction (i.e., perceived age), but the application of AI-based age prediction models to these questions is indeed highly novel.

II. An example output of the Aging Research Idea Generator

Here, we provided an exported idea generated by the ARIG that we also highlighted in Fig. 2.

The outputs of all of the 10 examined ideas are available in the Supplementary Files.

IDEA9:

Predicting Biological Age Recovery: Identifying Molecular and Physiological Markers of Stress-Induced Aging Reversibility

Generation ID: gen_2026-05-02T18-06-26_02lcf

Original Input Article

Title: Biological age is increased by stress and restored upon recovery.

Authors: Jesse R Poganik, Bohan Zhang, Gurpreet S Baht, Alexander Tyshkovskiy, Amy Deik, Csaba Kerepesi, Sun Hee Yim, Ake T Lu, Amin Haghani, Tong Gong, Anna M Hedman, Erika Andolf, Göran Pershagen, Catarina Almqvist, Clary B Clish, Steve Horvath, James P White, Vadim N Gladyshev

Journal: Cell metabolism

Year: 2023

PMID: 37086720

Abstract: Aging is classically conceptualized as an ever-increasing trajectory of damage accumulation and loss of function, leading to increases in morbidity and mortality. However, recent in vitro studies have raised the possibility of age reversal. Here, we report that biological age is fluid and exhibits rapid changes in both directions. At epigenetic, transcriptomic, and metabolomic levels, we find that the biological age of young mice is increased by heterochronic parabiosis and restored following surgical detachment. We also identify transient changes in biological age during major surgery, pregnancy, and severe COVID-19 in humans and/or mice. Together, these data show that biological age undergoes a rapid increase in response to diverse forms of stress, which is reversed following recovery from stress. Our study uncovers a new layer of aging dynamics that should be considered in future studies. The elevation of biological age by stress may be a quantifiable and actionable target for future interventions.

Short Hypothesis

Individual differences in biological age recovery following stress can be predicted by baseline molecular signatures and physiological resilience markers, enabling personalized interventions for accelerated aging reversal. While Poganik et al. demonstrated that biological age increases with stress and can recover afterward, the critical questions of *who* recovers, *how quickly*, and *what predicts* successful recovery remain unanswered. This represents a fundamental gap in our understanding of aging plasticity that, if addressed, could transform how we approach age-related interventions by identifying individuals most likely to benefit from specific recovery protocols.

Related Work

****Poganik et al. (Cell Metabolism, 2023)**** established that biological age increases with stress and recovers upon stress removal in mice and humans, but did not investigate individual differences in recovery dynamics or predictive markers. ****Pyrkov et al. (medRxiv, 2020)**** identified resilience markers from wearable sensors but focused on general health outcomes rather than biological age recovery specifically. ****Olde Rikkert et al. (Frontiers in Physiology, 2019)**** proposed dynamic resilience biomarkers for recovery prediction in geriatric medicine, but did not apply these concepts to epigenetic age or stress-induced aging. ****Recent epigenetic clock studies (Eder et al., 2025; Rodrigues et al., 2025)**** examine stress-aging relationships but treat biological age as a static outcome rather than investigating recovery dynamics. Our proposal uniquely focuses on the understudied recovery phase, combining baseline predictive markers with longitudinal recovery tracking to identify molecular determinants of aging reversibility.

Proposed Abstract

Biological age can increase rapidly under stress and recover afterward, but individual recovery varies dramatically. We propose to identify predictive markers of biological age recovery by conducting a longitudinal study of 200 healthy adults (25-65 years) undergoing planned surgical stress. Participants will be assessed at baseline, immediately post-surgery (stress peak), and during 6-month recovery using multiple epigenetic clocks (GrimAge2, DunedinPACE), transcriptomics, metabolomics, and physiological resilience markers. We hypothesize that baseline molecular signatures—including inflammatory gene expression patterns, mitochondrial function markers, and stress response pathway activity—will predict recovery speed and completeness. We will develop a machine learning model integrating baseline omics data, physiological measurements (heart rate variability, cortisol patterns), and demographic factors to predict individual recovery trajectories. This 'Recovery Predictor Score' will be validated in an independent cohort experiencing different stressors (intensive care patients). The study will establish the first systematic framework for predicting biological age recovery, potentially identifying individuals who would benefit most from specific interventions during the critical recovery window. This work could transform personalized anti-aging medicine by enabling targeted interventions for those at highest risk of persistent biological age acceleration.

Proposed Experiments

- ****Baseline Characterization****: Collect comprehensive baseline data from 200 surgical patients including epigenetic clocks (GrimAge2, DunedinPACE), RNA-seq, metabolomics, cortisol patterns, heart rate variability, inflammatory markers (IL-6, TNF- α , CRP), and mitochondrial function assays (Complex I activity, mtDNA copy number)
- ****Stress Response Tracking****: Measure biological age acceleration 48-72 hours post-surgery when stress-induced aging peaks, alongside acute stress markers and physiological parameters
- ****Recovery Monitoring****: Track biological age recovery at 2 weeks, 1 month, 3 months, and 6 months post-surgery, measuring both epigenetic age normalization and molecular pathway restoration
- ****Predictive Model Development****: Use machine learning (random forest, gradient boosting) to identify baseline molecular and physiological signatures that predict recovery speed (time to return to baseline biological age) and completeness (final biological age relative to baseline)

- **Validation Cohort**: Test the Recovery Predictor Score in 100 ICU patients experiencing different stressors, measuring prediction accuracy using correlation coefficients between predicted and observed recovery trajectories
- **Mechanistic Analysis**: Perform pathway enrichment analysis on predictive molecular signatures to identify key biological processes underlying recovery capacity, focusing on DNA repair, inflammatory resolution, and cellular stress response pathways

Risks & Limitations

- **Individual Variability**: High inter-individual differences in stress response and recovery may reduce predictive model accuracy, potentially requiring larger sample sizes or population stratification
- **Confounding Factors**: Surgical type, medications, and recovery conditions may introduce variability that complicates interpretation of recovery dynamics
- **Technical Limitations**: Current epigenetic clocks may lack sufficient sensitivity to detect rapid recovery changes, potentially requiring development of more dynamic aging biomarkers
- **Generalizability**: Recovery predictors identified in surgical stress may not apply to other stressors (psychological, environmental, disease-related), limiting broader applicability
- **Time-intensive Study**: 6-month longitudinal follow-up may result in participant dropout, potentially biasing results toward more compliant or healthier individuals
- **Cost Considerations**: Multi-omics profiling at multiple timepoints requires substantial resources, potentially limiting sample size and statistical power for subgroup analyses

III. Main codes (prompts) of the Aging Research Idea Generator

Below, we collected the main elements of the Aging Research Idea Generator. We adapted the workflow from the AI Scientist v2 tool of Sakana AI (https://github.com/SakanaAI/AI-Scientist-v2/blob/main/ai_scientist/perform_ideation_temp_free.py). We used a red background for the text where we made changes compared to the original code of the AI Scientist v2 code.

1. A system_prompt

```
system_prompt = ""
```

You are an experienced AI researcher tasked with proposing high-impact research ideas in the style of compelling grant proposals. We already have a previously published scientific paper, which has been provided as the "workshop description." Use this paper as the foundation for generating new, related research ideas.

Your proposals should be original, bold, and imaginative—think outside the box. Each idea should be grounded in a simple yet elegant question, observation, or hypothesis related to the original work. For example, proposals may include straightforward but insightful interventions or novel investigations that challenge existing assumptions or explore new possibilities.

Make sure each proposal clearly highlights how it differs from existing work in the literature.

The proposed ideas should be feasible within the resource constraints of a typical academic lab. Aim for proposals that could lead to publications in top aging journals.

You have access to the following tools:

```
{tool_descriptions}
```

```
"name": "LiteratureSearch",
```

```
"description": ""
```

Search for relevant literature using Pubmed, Google Search and Semantic Scholar services.

Provide a Semantic Scholar search query to find relevant papers. Query will be recompiled for each services.

```
""
```

```
{end_tool_descriptions}
```

```
{tool_descriptions}
```

```
"name": "FinalizeIdea",
```

```
"description": ""
```

Finalize your idea by providing the idea details.

The IDEA JSON should include the following fields:

- "Name": A short descriptor of the idea. Lowercase, no spaces, underscores allowed.

- "Title": **Plain text format** - A catchy and informative title for the proposal.

- "Short Hypothesis": **In Markdown format** - A concise statement of the main hypothesis or research question. Clarify the need for this specific direction, ensure this is the best setting to investigate this idea, and there are not obvious other simpler ways to answer the question.

- "Related Work": **In Markdown format** - A brief discussion of the most relevant related work and how the proposal clearly distinguishes from it, and is not a trivial extension. **Ensure related work referenced by paper Title, Author and Publish Date**

- "Abstract": **In Markdown format** - An abstract that summarizes the proposal in conference format (approximately 250 words).

- "Experiments": **In Markdown list format** - A list of experiments that would be conducted to validate the proposal. Ensure these are simple and feasible. Be specific in exactly how you would test the hypothesis, and detail precise algorithmic changes. Include the evaluation metrics you would use.

- "Risk Factors and Limitations": **In Markdown list format** - A list of potential risks and limitations of the proposal.

```
""
```

```
{end_tool_descriptions}
```

Chose only 1 ACTION with 1 ARGUMENTS

Respond in the following format:

ACTION:

```
<The action to take, exactly one of {tool_names_str}>
```

ARGUMENTS:

```
<If ACTION is " LiteratureSearch", provide the search query as {"query": "your search query"}. If ACTION is "FinalizeIdea", provide the idea details as {"idea": { ... }} with the IDEA JSON specified below.>
```

If you choose to finalize your idea, provide the IDEA JSON in the arguments:

IDEA JSON:

```
```json
```

```

{{
 "idea": {{
 "Name": "...",
 "Title": "...",
 "Short Hypothesis": "...",
 "Related Work": "...",
 "Abstract": "...",
 "Experiments": "...",
 "Risk Factors and Limitations": "..."
 }}
}}
...

```

Ensure the JSON is properly formatted for automatic parsing.

Note: You should perform at least one literature search before finalizing your idea to ensure it is well-informed by existing research.

"""

## 2. Prompt of the first idea:

```
idea_generation_prompt = """
```

Here is the workshop description:

```
{workshop_description}
```

Here are the proposals that you have already generated:

"""

```
{prev_ideas_string}
```

"""

Begin by generating an interestingly new high-level research proposal that differs from what you have previously proposed.

"""

## 3. The reflection prompt:

```
idea_reflection_prompt = """Round {current_round}/{num_reflections}.
```

In your thoughts, first carefully consider the quality, novelty, and feasibility of the proposal you just created.

I repeat make sure the proposal is novel and not a trivial extension of existing work. Consider whether the proposal is well-grounded in the workshop description and whether it has the potential for high impact. Reflect on any weaknesses or limitations in the proposal, and how it could be improved.

If you have doubts, then refine the proposal to address those doubts and redo the novelty check with LiteratureSearch search.

Include any other factors that you think are important in evaluating the proposal.

Ensure the proposal is clear and concise, and the JSON is in the correct format.

Do not make things overly complicated.

In the next attempt, try to refine and improve your proposal.

Stick to the spirit of the original idea unless there are glaring issues.

If you have new information from tools, such as literature search results, incorporate them into your reflection and refine your proposal accordingly.

Results from your last action (if any):

{last\_tool\_results}

""

#### 4. The FinalizeIdea tool definition:

"name": "FinalizeIdea",

"description": ""

Finalize your idea by providing the idea details.

The IDEA JSON should include the following fields:

- "Name": A short descriptor of the idea. Lowercase, no spaces, underscores allowed.
- "Title": Plain text format - A catchy and informative title for the proposal.
- "Short Hypothesis": In Markdown format - A concise statement of the main hypothesis or research question. Clarify the need for this specific direction, ensure this is the best setting to investigate this idea, and there are not obvious other simpler ways to answer the question.
- "Related Work": In Markdown format - A brief discussion of the most relevant related work and how the proposal clearly distinguishes from it, and is not a trivial extension. Ensure related work referenced by paper Title, Author and Publish Date
- "Abstract": In Markdown format - An abstract that summarizes the proposal in conference format (approximately 250 words).
- "Experiments": In Markdown list format - A list of experiments that would be conducted to validate the proposal. Ensure these are simple and feasible. Be specific in exactly how you would test the hypothesis, and detail precise algorithmic changes. Include the evaluation metrics you would use.
- "Risk Factors and Limitations": In Markdown list format - A list of potential risks and limitations of the proposal.

""

#### 5. Description of the Search tool:

"name": "LiteratureSearch",

"description": ""

Search for relevant literature using Pubmed, Google Search and Semantic Scholar services.

Provide a Semantic Scholar search query to find relevant papers. Query will be recompiled for each services.

""